

ISic0081

I.Sicily inscription 0081

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance

Found in the surface layers of refuse on top of a layer of early modern fill which post-dates 1619, in the north tower of the Duomo of Cefalu cathedral

Coordinates

38.040004, 14.023205

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble plaque, broken to left and below

Dimensions

Height 25 cm

Width 18.7 cm

Depth 5 cm

Layout

Remains of five lines of Latin letters, decreasing in size, with uneven right margin.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Di]s Ma

2. ñibus

3. [---]i!|ae

4. [---]ae

5. [---]m

Apparatus

Text based upon poor quality photo in Tullio 1995

Translation

Commentary

If the heading 'Dis Manibus' is written out in full over the first two lines, as

appears to be the case, this approximately fixes the width of the stone, and suggests a single female name in genitive or dative on each of lines 3 and 4. The name in line 3 is either ILLAE or ILIAE/

Digital identifiers:

TM 644814

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1997-1998. Epigrafia Latina. *Kokalos*. 43-44: 613-624. At 614

Tullio, A. 1995. Le torri del duomo di Cefalu. Esplorazione archeologica 1985-1986.. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 87-89: 143-159. At 151-153 fig.21

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